

The Network of Advisors in Short Food Supply Chains across Europe

Multi-actor collaboration dynamics and capacity building network inside and between AKIS to foster the upscaling of SFSCs across Europe

What do we want to get?

Identify and characterize SFSC advisors across Europe

Connect SFSC advisors from the 27 MSs in a European network

Improve the understanding of the main issues and challenges of European AKIS

Integrate SFSC advisors and contents into national AKIS

Interact with relevant national, regional & local policy-makers

Replicate and disseminate innovations on SFSC

How are we going to make it?

Living Labs:

4 labs testing innovative governance models with advisors, researchers, policymakers, farmers, and consumers.

Capacity Building:

Facilitating knowledge transfer to empower SFSC actors.

Advisor Integration:

Boosting advisors' roles in translating research into practice and integrating them into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).

What to expect?

Short food supply chains (SFSC) are a mean for both producers and consumers to gain better positions in the value chain, improving trust, transparency, food quality and safety. The EU-funded EU4Advice project aims to bolster SFSC-related advisory services to chain actors, to help them make their practices more economically, socially and environmentally sustainable, connecting SFSC-advisors from the 27 member States in a common network, integrating SFSC-related advisory services, tools and contents into national Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), and improving AKIS governance.

A network of 4 Living Labs to test innovative governance models, involving advisors, researchers, policy-makers, farmers and consumers

Boost the role of advisors as catalysers of the knowledge flow from research to practice

Effective capacity building of SFSC actors through fluent knowledge transfer

Effective integration of SFSC advisors into national AKIS

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